

Inverse-design of two-dimensional magnonic crystals via topology optimization with frequency-domain micromagnetics

Ryunosuke Nagaoka¹, Takahiro Yamazaki^{1,2}, Chiharu Mitsumata³,

Yuma Iwasaki⁴, and Masato Kotsugi¹

¹Department of Materials Science and Technology, Tokyo University of Science, Tokyo, Japan.

²Faculty of Engineering, Yokohama National University, Yokohama, Japan

³Graduate School of Pure and Applied Sciences, University of Tsukuba, Ibaraki, Japan.

⁴Center for Basic Research on Materials (CBRM), National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), Ibaraki, Japan.

February 12, 2026

Abstract

Magnonic crystals (MCs) are emerging spintronic metamaterials capable of manipulating transmission properties of magnons, the quanta of spin waves. Due to the complex relationship between geometric patterns and magnonic band dispersion, it remains challenging to establish general design strategies for optimizing targeted properties in MCs. In this study, we demonstrate an inverse-design framework for two-dimensional MCs to explore novel lattice structures. We employ genetic algorithms to enable global exploration of structures that maximize complete magnonic band gap, and also adopt frequency-domain micromagnetic simulations to improve the computational efficiency and accuracy of band gap evaluation in the design-optimization loop. Our established inverse-design framework successfully discovered some novel designs of MCs and their performance was validated using time-domain micromagnetic simulations. Furthermore, we observed that the design landscape is highly non-convex, especially for high-order band numbers. This inverse-design framework is expected to be broadly applicable to other material systems and device length scales relevant to experimental conditions, facilitating the formulation of design rules for MCs.

1 Introduction

Spin waves (SWs) are collective magnetization excitations that propagate in a phase-coherent manner and have attracted considerable attention as information carriers for beyond-CMOS technologies [1,2]. A wide range of applications has been proposed and experimentally demonstrated, including logic circuits [3,4] memory device [5] physical neural networks [6], and neuromorphic computing architectures [7–10]. Among these applications, magnonic crystals (MCs), in which magnetic hosting materials of SWs are periodically modulated in space, have been proposed as metamaterial structures for tailoring the dispersion relationship of magnons. Such periodic structures promote coherent SW scattering, which gives rise to designed magnonic band dispersions and wave functions. One- [11], two- [12], and three-dimensional [13] MCs have been investigated both experimentally and theoretically. In addition, the resulting characteristics are flexibly tunable through external magnetic fields and ferroelectricity. This tunability places MCs as magnetic counterparts of photonic crystals, which manipulate electromagnetic waves [14], and phononic crystals, which manipulate elastic waves [15]. Geometric engineering of MCs has been widely explored as a route to design SW transport. For instance, nonreciprocal SW propagation and dispersion modulation can be achieved by introducing arbitrary unit cell geometries [16–19] and controlling the lattice symmetry [20,21]. Among the resulting functionalities, magnonic band gaps (MBGs), where magnon propagation is prohibited along specific excitation frequency, have become a central design target because they are highly tunable through geometry and straightforward to measure experimentally [22].

However, due to its complex relations between lattice geometry and magnonic dispersions, comprehensive design rules for enlarging MBGs and the optimal geometry for achieving the widest MBG remain unclear. In most previous studies, desired propagation characteristics have been obtained by parametrically sweeping shape-related parameters, such as the scatterer radius and volume fraction, to identify optimal configurations [23]. Furthermore, many conventional studies focus on targeting lower-order bands (such as 1st to 3rd band), thus higher-order bands, which could realize higher design flexibility, have not been extensively investigated.

In this context, one promising strategy for exploring optimal structures is the inverse-design approach, in which target physical properties are defined as objective functions and parametrized design region are optimized through mathematical optimization methods. This approach allows flexible structural exploration and significantly expands the design space for realizing nontrivial device designs. Recently, inverse-design approaches have begun to be incorporated into SW device design. For example, optimizing spatial distributions of materials has enabled the design of SW lense [24] and frequency demultiplexers [25]. In addition, engineering optimally designed local magnetic field profiles has enabled improved control over SW demultiplexing characteristics and enhanced logic-operation accuracy [26,27].

Notably, Voronov et al. recently demonstrated topology optimization using a level-set method and designed high-efficiency frequency demultiplexer of spin waves [28]. In parallel, several open-source tools are being developed to implement topology optimization in micromagnetics [29,30]. These

approaches typically rely on time-domain micromagnetic simulations to evaluate propagation characteristics; however, obtaining broadband frequency responses with high spectral resolution can be computationally expensive, and eigenmodes are not obtained directly.

In this study, we combine frequency-domain micromagnetic simulations, which are well suited for frequency analysis in the linear spin-wave regime, with a genetic algorithm (GA) to enable efficient inverse design of magnonic crystals. The unit-cell material distribution is represented using a binary (0/1) genetic encoding, enabling systematic exploration of the discrete material-design space to identify unconventional device topologies. As the model property, we maximize the complete MBGs, with particular emphasis on higher-order band gaps that have not been extensively investigated.

Our objective is to identify previously unexplored MC designs exhibiting wide complete-MBG. As further investigations, we validate the optimized designs via time-domain micromagnetic simulation and conduct an unsupervised machine learning analysis to visualize design landscape of the optimized structures, thereby providing design guidelines for MCs. The proposed framework is expected to be broadly extensible to the design of a wide range of MC systems.

2 Methodology for inverse design of MCs

In this study, we explore novel designs of two-dimensional magnonic crystals (2D MCs) by implementing an inverse-design loop based on iterative feedback calculations of objective quantities (complete MBGs). We employ frequency-domain micromagnetic simulation framework, which is based on the frequency-domain Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert (FD-LLG) equation and the finite element method (FEM), to evaluate MBGs. Magnonic dispersion relations are typically calculated either from time-domain micromagnetic simulations combined with spatiotemporal fast Fourier transforms (FFT) [31] or by semi-analytical approaches such as the plane wave method (PWM) [32]. In contrast, FD-LLG simulations provide an efficient and accurate route to estimating dispersion relations for structures with arbitrary geometries represented by fine spatial discretization. The FD-LLG equation is obtained by linearizing the magnetization dynamics assuming the small deviations from an equilibrium state; details of the formulation are provided in the Methods section. The resulting FD-LLG equation is expressed as follows [33]:

$$i\omega\delta\mathbf{m} = -\gamma\mathbf{m}_0 \times \delta\mathbf{h}^{\text{eff}} - \gamma\delta\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{h}_0^{\text{eff}} + i\omega\alpha\mathbf{m}_0 \times \delta\mathbf{m} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{m}_0 and $\mathbf{h}_0^{\text{eff}}$ are the static (equilibrium) components, and $\delta\mathbf{m}$ and $\delta\mathbf{h}^{\text{eff}}$ are the dynamic components of magnetization and effective field, respectively. By solving this equation as eigen value problem, it is possible to acquire set of the eigenfrequencies ω and the eigenmodes of $\delta\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ to perform mode analysis. In this study, regarding the effective field terms, only the exchange field

and external field were considered for static and dynamic component as $\mathbf{h}_0^{\text{eff}} = A\nabla^2\mathbf{m}_0 + \mathbf{h}_0$ and $\mathbf{h}^{\text{eff}} = A\nabla^2\delta\mathbf{m} + \delta\mathbf{h}$. This approximation ensures that SWs are excited in the exchange mode. The MCs considered in this study have a lattice constant comparable to the exchange length, and it is expected that the overall optimization trends will not change significantly even if the magnetostatic (demagnetizing) field is neglected. Therefore, we omit the computationally expensive magnetostatic-field calculation for an initial validation of the inverse-design algorithm.

For calculating dispersion relationship, the discretized unit cell approximation was considered as shown in Figure 1a. We selected a bicomponent MC composed of Europium oxide (EuO) and Iron (Fe) as the model system. This material combination is favorable for opening wide complete MBG, our target property in this study, due to its high contrast in material parameters. We used a cuboid mesh with a side length of 2 nm, which is sufficiently small to capture the effects of exchange interactions. The lattice constant of the MC was set to $a=32$ nm. This is because in general, an appropriate lattice size where exchange interaction is predominant for SW propagation is below 100 nm [32]. In addition, as a boundary condition, Bloch-Floquet boundaries were applied in the x and y direction as shown in the Figure 1a. This boundary condition allows the periodicity of both phase and amplitude of $\delta\mathbf{h}$ and $\delta\mathbf{m}$ as a Bloch periodicity. Static magnetic field \mathbf{h}_0 was applied perpendicular to the film, which was set to 0.1 T, and the static equilibrium magnetization was assumed to be uniform in z direction, thus unit vector of $\mathbf{m}_0 = (0, 0, 1)$. the simulation parameters for individual materials were set as follows: for EuO, $A_{ex}^{EuO} = 0.1 \times 10^{-11}$ J/m and $M_s^{EuO} = 1.91 \times 10^6$ A/m; for Fe, $A_{ex}^{Fe} = 2.11 \times 10^{-11}$ J/m and $M_s^{Fe} = 1.752 \times 10^6$ A/m [34]. Since the analysis focuses on exchange-dominated SW modes, only the exchange stiffness constant A_{ex} and the saturation magnetization M_s are considered as material-dependent parameters, because the analytical formulation of dispersion relation of exchange mode magnons in a single medium is given by $\omega(k) = \gamma\mu_0[\frac{2A_{ex}}{M_s}k^2 + H_{eff}]$ [35]. Damping constant α was set to 0.001 for both materials. Furthermore, when defining material distribution, we defined only one-eighth of total area, utilizing the mirror symmetry, as indicated by red frame in the unit cell shown in Figure 1a. This allows the definition of material distribution only in the region of interest, reducing the dimension of design variables. The calculation described above was implemented by utilizing a third-party micromagnetic module provided in finite element simulation software COMSOL Multiphysics with the eigenvalue problem solved by solver package ARPACK [33].

Figure 1b shows the band dispersion calculated for the square-circular MCs illustrated in Figure 1a using FD-LLG methods. The band structure reveals the emergence of a frequency range in which magnons are not excited in any propagation direction. This frequency range corresponds to a "complete" MBG. We focus on this property as a model target to investigate the optimal geometry that maximizes complete MBG in Fe-EuO system.

Figure 1c illustrates the conceptual schematic of the design-optimization loop targeting to maximize complete MBG of MCs. In this study, we adopted a binary encoding scheme and employed a GA as the optimization engine. The GA is a well-established metaheuristic algorithm inspired by natural selection and biological evolution, which was originally developed in the field of bio-inspired comput-

Figure 1: a) Schematic illustration of two-dimensional MC composed of EuO matrix and Fe circular dot. Spatially discretized unit cell structure of MC and the schematic image of 1st Brillouin zone are shown below. b) Corresponding dispersion relationship calculated on unit cell shown in a). c) Conceptual schematic of the inverse-design loop implemented in this study.

ing [36]. Because GA is a stochastic, gradient-free method, it is well suited to global optimization problems and is expected to discover unconventional MC geometries that realize large MBGs, which may be difficult to obtain using parametric sweeping of simple shape-related quantities. In the proposed inverse-design loop, the material distribution in a unit cell is represented by a binary vector (0/1) with the length of 36, which is regarded as a genetic sequence. The optimization proceeds

iteratively by repeating the following steps: (1) definition of the unit-cell material distribution, (2) evaluation of the band gaps using FD-LLG simulations, and (3) generation of the next population by GA operations (selection, crossover, and mutation). (4) Create bit arrays in new generation and redefine unit cell. Through this loop, the discretized cell structure is gradually transformed toward designs with larger band gaps. As an illustrative example, Figure 1c also shows a sequence of structural evolution during optimization. By iterating the loop, the initially discretized topology is progressively updated and converges to a non-empirical topology that differs substantially from conventional analytical shape. Notably, during the evolution process, the emergence and disappearance of holes and isolated islands can be observed, indicating discontinuous topological changes. Such non-continuous topology transformations enable the proposal of previously unexplored MC topologies.

Figure 2: Algorithm chart of design optimization process

Next, we describe the algorithmic formulation of inverse-design process in detail. The optimization problem to maximize MBG width is formulated as follows

$$\begin{cases} \text{maximize } f_n(\boldsymbol{\rho}) & \text{w.r.t. } \boldsymbol{\rho} \in \{0, 1\}^N \quad (N = 36) \\ f_n(\boldsymbol{\rho}) = \frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_c} = \frac{\min_k : \omega_{n+1}(\mathbf{k}) - \max_k : \omega_n(\mathbf{k})}{\frac{1}{2}[\min_k : \omega_{n+1}(\mathbf{k}) + \max_k : \omega_n(\mathbf{k})]} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Here, $f_n(\boldsymbol{\rho})$ is an objective function, same as target property, defined as relative band gap between n th and $(n + 1)$ th bands. \mathbf{k} is wave vector, and $\Delta\omega$, ω_c are absolute value of MBG and center frequency between band gaps, respectively. This relative band gap width is typically used for evaluating band gap width as a scale-invariant parameter in inverse design of photonic and phononic crystals [37, 38]. $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ is a binary density variable of material with the dimension of $N=36$, which is allocated in each finite element cells. By using this density variable, the material parameters are defined as $A_{ex}(\rho_i) = (1 - \rho_i)A_{ex}^{EuO} + \rho_i A_{ex}^{Fe}$ and $M_s(\rho_i) = (1 - \rho_i)M_s^{EuO} + \rho_i M_s^{Fe}$. When $\rho_i = 0$, the i -th cell is assigned to the parameters of EuO, whereas when $\rho_i = 1$, it assigned to those of Fe. This means that there are $2^{36} \approx 10^{10}$ possible material distributions, making it impractical to find the optimal solution using exhaustive search. Figure 2b shows the algorithm chart of design optimization process. Firstly, the initial distribution was generated randomly. The number of generated feature vectors, which is called population, was set to $P=20$. With the binary-encoded 0/1 vector generated, it is possible to map material distribution onto each finite element cell. Then, the FD-LLG simulation was performed to evaluate the MBG width for each design. Before band gap evaluation, we applied a density-filtering step to suppress spurious, noise-like features in the topology. Specifically, isolated bits whose neighborhood predominantly consists of the opposite bits were flipped to match the surrounding bits. This filtering removes dot-like artifacts that are unfavorable for fabrication and improves the robustness of optimized designs. After evaluating MBG width, the natural selection process, a core process in GA, was performed to find candidate structure. The detailed process of GA is described as following:

1. Selection: This process was performed based on the evaluation results of the objective function. We employed the Roulette Wheel Selection method. In this scheme, the probability of an individual being selected is directly proportional to its fitness value (i.e., the relative band gap). This implies that individuals with better performance have a higher probability of passing their genes to the next generation. The probability of selecting individual can be expressed as $q_i = f_i / \sum_j f_j$.

2. Crossover: This operation promotes the recombination of genetic information and facilitates the exploration of the solution space while preserving the structural characteristics of the parents. A two-point crossover operator was applied to the gene vectors selected in the former process, where two crossover points were randomly selected and the segments between them were exchanged between

the pair of parent vectors.

3. Mutation: This process was introduced to maintain genetic diversity and prevent the algorithm from converging to local optima. A bit-flip mutation method was employed, in which each bit in the gene vector is inverted (switched from 0 to 1, or vice versa) with a mutation probability of $1/N$. This stochastic variation enables the algorithm to escape local optima and explore new regions of the search space.

After this sequence of selection, crossover, and mutation, a new generation with the same number of P is produced, and the same procedure is repeated until a convergence criterion is met; specifically, the optimization is terminated when the fitness value fails to improve for more than a prescribed number of generations M (Here, we set $M = 50$). Through this process, a candidate structure exhibiting a large MBG is ultimately obtained. The whole optimization process explained above was implemented using MATLAB [39].

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Inverse-design demonstration

As an initial demonstration of inverse-design exploration, we focus on searching for structures maximizing the complete band gap between the modes of $n=2$ and $n=3$, which has been most extensively analyzed in previous studies. Figure 3a shows the structural evolution of the MC during the optimization process. As the iterations proceed, the MBG is observed to increase through a sequence of transformations, starting from $\Delta\omega/\omega_c = 0.331$ to 0.598. We see that the transformation process includes changes in connectivity and the generation and annihilation of holes, hence topological transformation was observed.

Ultimately, the MBG value converges to 0.598 at the 200th generation. While the best fitness in each generation is progressively improved through optimization, the average fitness of the population does not converge and instead continues to fluctuate. This indicates that, although the algorithm refines the best solution, the population simultaneously explores other regions of the design space, thereby maintaining global exploration successfully.

Figure 3c shows the band dispersions calculated for the best individuals in the initial and final populations. Comparison of the two dispersions reveals that optimization shifts the bands above the third mode toward higher frequencies. The final optimized structure closely resembles the square-square-square (SSS) structure (shown in Figure 5a, rotated by 45°). This geometry represents a promising candidate for opening a gap between the second and third bands, as the introduction of additional scatterers at face-centered positions in a square lattice is known to promote MBG formation [40]. The 45° rotation increases the filling fraction of scatterers within the unit cell, which is likely responsible

for the observed wide MBG.

Figure 3: a) Topological deformation of MC design during the optimization process maximizing MBG between $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ mode. Note that the unit cell is expanded to 3×3 matrix for visualization. b) The history of change of fitness value (MBG) along generation. c) Dispersion relationship of the best individual in 1st generation and final generation.

As a result, the nonempirical optimization focusing on the second-third MBG yields structures that are consistent with established theoretical understanding of wide-MBG MCs. The absence of contradictions in the optimization results confirms that the present framework successfully identifies structures that maximize the MBG between the 2nd and 3rd band. However, Figure 3c further reveals that while the dispersions of the 1st and 2nd band remain largely unchanged, the higher-frequency bands are found to be highly sensitive to the spatial distribution of materials. This means that the high-order dispersion relation has higher controllability by geometric designing but also indicates that there is a complex relationship between the lattice geometry and its resulting band structure. Such complexity has hindered the establishment of clear design guidelines for MCs in high band mode numbers. Hence optimal structures for gaps between higher order bands have not yet been systematically explored in prior studies.

3.2 Optimal design in higher-order bands

We next targeted higher-order ($n \geq 3$) MBG width as an objective function and performed topology optimization. Figure 4a shows the optimized structures for the MBGs at each band number together with their corresponding band dispersions. Each optimized structure shows non-trivial designs which have not been proposed previously. Focusing on the optimized structures for individual bands, we find that the structures for band 3-4, 5-6, 6-7, and 7-8 exhibit EuO lines (white lines) crossing perpendicularly with oriented at 45° with respect to the Floquet wave vector. Particularly intriguing is the optimized structure for band 4-5, which consists of a simple arrangement of square Fe dots. To our knowledge, such a geometry has not previously been proposed as a wide-MBG MC, indicating that the present optimization reveals a previously overlooked structure in Fe-EuO MCs. Focusing on the structural trends along with band numbers, as the target band gap number increases, the structural features become progressively complicated and slim connection of structures appear. This trend is physically reasonable, since higher-order eigenmodes correspond to shorter-wavelength magnons, which are expected to resonate with structures of smaller characteristic length scales. Furthermore, this increase of slim connection was also observed in the topology optimization of photonic crystals [37]. This similarity can be understood within the approximation considered here, as exchange mode SWs propagate isotropically with respect to the external-field direction, leading MCs to exhibit behavior analogous to that of photonic crystals.

Motivated by its simple geometry and wide absolute gap width, we focus on the optimized band 4-5 structure and visualize the spatial distribution of the x component magnetization perturbation $\delta m_x(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ at the Γ point for the relevant eigenmodes. The results show that, for bands below the lower edge of the gap, the eigenmodes are localized within the square Fe dots, whereas for bands above the upper edge of the gap, the modes are localized within the EuO line regions. This contrast in mode localization is likely responsible for the formation of the wide MBG in the optimized structure. By independently optimizing MBGs for different band indices, we identify a variety of unconventional wide-MBG MC structures that have not been proposed in previous studies.

Furthermore, we show the comparison analysis of optimized lattice structure with conventionally proposed structures. Figure 5a shows previously proposed square-lattice MC structures as wide-MBG configurations. Considering the mirror symmetry shown in Figure 1a, the representative comparison structures with same symmetry were selected. Wang et al. performed a thorough and systematic exhaustive search and successfully determined the optimal lattice parameters of these structures focusing on maximizing MBG between $n=2$ and $n=3$ [40]. This was realized by systematically sweeping the volume fraction of the rods (Fe) and the rod aspect ratio β shown in the figure 5a. Several studies have also examined MBGs for higher-order bands ($n > 3$) in some of these lattice designs. However, to the best of our knowledge, a systematic investigation of the optimal designs for $n > 3$ has not yet been reported.

The results of comparative analysis of the relative band gap are summarized in Figure 5b. For each

Figure 4: a) Optimization results for different band numbers and corresponding dispersion relationships b) Spatial mode profile of δm_x at the Γ point for the band 4-5 optimized structure.

structure, the band gap values were obtained by parametric sweeping of the Fe volume fraction and the shape parameter β described in Figure 5a, so as to maximize the gap width for each band. The detail results of the parametric sweeps over f and β are provided in the Supplemental Material. The comparison indicates that, except for the band 2-3 gap, the topology-optimized structures obtained in this study exhibit larger MBGs than all previously proposed structures. This demonstrates that the proposed framework is capable of discovering structures with superior MBG performance beyond conventional designs. Notably, MBG between $n=3$ and $n=4$ is observed only in the topology-optimized structure, whereas none of the previously proposed structures exhibit a gap in this band range. A possible reason the band 2-3 gap does not exceed that of previous designs is that the present approach represents structures on a finite, discretized cell grid, which inherently limits the geometric precision of the resulting designs. Employing a finer mesh would increase the degrees of freedom in shape representation and could therefore improve the optimality of the discovered structures. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that our framework identifies high-order optimal geometries in Fe-EuO-based MCs that have been largely unexplored.

Figure 5: a) Schematic illustrations of previously investigated lattice structure. b) Comparison of maximum band gap value with previously proposed magnonic crystal lattice. The band gap value refers to the one optimized by the shape-related variable shown in (a). "NBG" means no band gap was observed.

3.3 Time-domain evaluation of optimized design

To validate the structures optimized using frequency-domain simulations, we calculate magnon excitation spectra using MuMax3, a standard finite-difference time-domain micromagnetic simulator [41]. We selected this simulator due to its widespread use, which supports reproducibility and comparability of our results. For spectral calculations, broadband magnon excitation is achieved by injecting a sinc pulse into the optimized lattice, as illustrated in Figure 6a. The magnetic field sinc pulse is described by

$$B_{pulse}(t) = B_0 \frac{\sin[2\pi f_{max}(t - t_0)]}{2\pi f_{max}(t - t_0)} \quad (3)$$

The excitation waveform parameters were set to $B_0 = 0.01$ T and $f_{max} = 25$ GHz. The reference time was set to be $t_0 = T/2$, where T is the total running time of 30 ns. The cell size is set to 2 nm consistent with the one used in frequency-domain design optimization. The unit cell was extended to $1.024 \mu\text{m} \times 1.024 \mu\text{m}$ in the x and y directions to create supercell, and the periodic boundary

condition (PBC) was applied to x and y direction. The sinc pulse was applied at the center of the supercell. The same material parameters as those used in the frequency-domain calculations are employed. Then, the magnon excitation spectra was obtained by performing a temporal FFT of the excited SW time-series data.

Figure 6: a) Schematic illustrate of time-domain verification of optimized structures. Broadband SW was excited by adding sinc pulse in the center of extended supercell of optimized lattice. b) FFT spectrum of excited SW for optimized structures.

The calculated excitation spectra are shown in Figure 6b. For all optimized structures, the presence of MBGs is clearly confirmed by the absence of magnon excitation within specific frequency ranges. These results indicate that the optimized structures exhibit complete MBG within the considered frequency ranges. Notably, as expected in frequency-domain study, the optimized structure of

band 4-5 shows large MBG (approximately 11.7 GHz in width). For the band 5-6 optimized structure, the gap frequency range obtained from the time-domain analysis do not coincide exactly with those obtained from the frequency-domain simulations. This might be attributable to differences in the boundary conditions employed in the two approaches. Overall, the results of time-domain magnon excitation support the existence of complete MBGs and the validity of optimized MC design.

3.4 Visualization of design landscape

To statistically evaluate the optimized lattice designs, we systematically performed many inverse-design loops using different random seeds to generate the initial structures for each run, reducing the dependence of the optimization results on the initial conditions. Furthermore, to visualize the design exploration space, we performed dimension reduction using unsupervised machine learning method on all design bit arrays generated during the optimization process and mapped them into two-dimensional feature space.

For dimensional reduction, we employed combination 2D FFT with multidimensional scaling (MDS), one of the dimensionality reduction techniques. MDS can represent high-dimensional data in a low-dimensional data space by preserving distances in original space, allowing high interpretability in clustering and similarity analysis. The detailed process is depicted in Figure 7a. First, each 36-dimensional design vector was expanded into a unit-cell array (16×16), and a 2D FFT was applied to obtain the Fourier spectrum and extract information of structural periodicity. The Fourier spectrum was then flattened into a 256-dimensional vector, and MDS based on Euclidean distances was performed to reduce the dimensionality from 256 to 2. For MDS calculation, scikit-learn, a Python package for machine learning, was used [42].

Figure 7b shows the MDS mappings for each band index. The color map represents the relative band gap value of each structure, and each point corresponds to a unit-cell geometry. For the band 2-3, band 3-4, and band 4-5 gaps, structures with large band gaps (marked by stars) form localized clusters in the reduced space. This indicates that the optimization process converges toward similar structures for these band gap numbers. In contrast, for the band 5-6, band 6-7, and band 7-8 gaps, the optimized structures are more broadly distributed, and the structural similarity between solutions is significantly lower. These results suggest that, in higher-order bands, the optimization yields different solutions across runs and admits multiple local optima, implying that the design landscape is highly non-convex. While the presence of many candidate solutions implies greater design flexibility for tailoring dispersion relations, it also indicates that identifying a globally optimal structure becomes increasingly difficult. Finally, from a physical perspective, higher-order resonances can support multiple resonance modes because the increased degrees of freedom in finer geometries allow a larger number of possible configurations.

In addition, as an additional metric to quantify the complexity of the optimized structures as a function of band numbers, we introduce the Shannon information entropy. We expected this to

(a) Process of MDS visualization

Figure 7: a) MDS mapping of unit cell structures for each band numbers. Colormap represents MBG value, and the star marker represents the final optimal design. b) Correlation of information entropy calculated from unit cell structure and relative band gap.

enable the quantification of structural complexity along with increasing band numbers observed in the optimization results in Figure 4. Shannon entropy describes configurational entropy in Heisenberg spin models and utilized as a measure of geometrical complexity in metasurface structures [43] as

$$S = -[\log_2 x + \log_2(1 - x)], \quad x = \frac{V_{EuO}}{V_{total}} \quad (4)$$

Here, V_{EuO} , V_{total} denotes the volume of the EuO phase and total volume of unit cell, respectively. In the entropy calculation, 2×2 kernel was prepared, and the entropy within randomly sampled kernels in the unit cell was evaluated 100 times, then the averaged value $S_{ave} = \frac{1}{100} \sum_{i=1}^{100} S_i$ was used for analysis. This procedure enables the evaluation of local configurational fluctuations of the unit cell to be characterized.

Figure 7c shows the correlation between the entropy of the final optimized structures and the corresponding band gap widths for each band. Although the results for the band 1-2 optimization are out of scope, they are also included to provide an overall trend (typically optimized to SS lattice structure). As seen in the MDS analysis, the data for band 2-3, 3-4, and 4-5 form distinct clusters, indicating that structures with similar entropy values and band gap widths are concentrated in these bands. In contrast, the data for band 5-6, 6-7, and 7-8 exhibit a broader dispersion, reflecting increased structural diversity. Moreover, we see that there is a positive correlation between band number and entropy, consistent with the progressive structural refinement observed in higher-order bands. These results indicate that low-order band gaps are associated with simpler structures with small amounts of information, whereas higher-order band gaps require structures with increased geometrical complexity. This finding suggests that Shannon Entropy provides a useful quantitative descriptor of MC geometries and can serve as a practical guideline for structural design. We expect that this approach for visualizing the design landscape and quantifying design features can be extended to experimentally feasible material systems and device length scales, thereby fostering the understanding of practical design guidelines for MCs.

4 Conclusions

In this study, we demonstrated inverse-design topology optimization of two-dimensional MCs, which has not been previously demonstrated. By combining a GA with FD-LLG simulations, we efficiently identify a number of promising structures in higher-order bands that have remained unexplored. These results highlight the effectiveness of expanding the design space through high-dimensional structural exploration in MC design. Through systematic comparison with structures proposed in previous studies, we show that the topology-optimized structures can achieve larger MBG widths than conventional designs. Notably, the design optimized for the MBG between the 4th and 5th bands is particularly promising owing to its structural simplicity and the sufficiently large band gap width of 11.7 GHz. The existence of these wide MBGs is further confirmed by conventional time-domain LLG simulations using MuMax3, demonstrating the reliability of frequency-domain-based optimization. In addition, the dimensional reduction of MDS further reveals that the convergence behavior of the optimization depends on the band numbers, indicating that the design landscape becomes increasingly non-convex for higher-order bands. This implies that multiple distinct candidate designs exist, and that a variety of magnon’s resonance modes can be supported. Furthermore, we introduce information entropy as a metric for quantifying the structural complexity of MCs and find a positive correlation between the band number and the entropy. This result indicates that MC structures with an appropriate information amount should be selected according to the target band index. Overall, our findings demonstrate the usefulness of information entropy as a structural descriptor for MC design.

5 Method- Formulation of FD-LLG equation

In micromagnetics, the magnetization dynamics are governed by the time-dependent LLG equation, given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}}{\partial t} = -\gamma \mathbf{m} \times [\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{m}) + \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{r}, t)] + \alpha \mathbf{m} \times \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}}{\partial t} \quad (5)$$

where γ is the gyromagnetic ratio, α is the Gilbert damping constant, \mathbf{H}_{eff} is the effective magnetic field. To convert the LLG equation from the time domain to the frequency domain, the magnetization and effective field are decomposed into a static equilibrium background and a small dynamic perturbation

$$\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \mathbf{m}_0(\mathbf{r}) + \delta \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \mathbf{h}_0^{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}) + \delta \mathbf{h}^{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (7)$$

There is an assumption that the excitation of moment is weak enough to consider linear approximation ($\delta \mathbf{m} \ll \mathbf{m}_0$). Under linear SW excitation, dynamic components of both the magnetization and magnetic field can be expressed as harmonic functions by Fourier transform as

$$\delta \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \delta \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) e^{i\omega t} \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{h}^{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \mathbf{h}^{\text{eff}}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) e^{i\omega t} \quad (9)$$

This approximation allows to shadow time-dependent LLG equation into frequency space. By substituting Eq. (6)-(9) into Eq. (5), the FD-LLG are given in the form shown in Eq. (1). Furthermore, by solving Eq. (1) as an eigenvalue problem, it is possible to calculate the eigenmodes of $\delta \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$, enabling the calculation of the SW dispersion relation of MCs by \mathbf{k} scanning. This was implemented by applying the Bloch-Floquet boundary condition in the periodic direction. The Bloch-Floquet condition allows periodicity in both the amplitude and phase of physical quantities, expressed by

$$\delta\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{R}) = \delta\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot e^{-i\mathbf{k}_F \cdot \mathbf{R}} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{k}_F is a Floquet wave vector. In 2D MCs, this boundary condition must be set in x, y direction. By solving the eigenmodes for each \mathbf{k}_F , it is possible to calculate the SW dispersion in the form of a $k - \omega$ ($k - f$) diagram. In this study, calculations were performed within the first Brillouin zone illustrated in Figure 1c. Additionally, this periodic approximation allows us to restrict the computational domain to a single unit cell. While most conventional numerical methods solve this equation in the time domain, a frequency-domain formulation offers significant advantages in both speed and accuracy for studying SW spectra, eigenmodes under linear excitations.

6 Acknowledgements

This work was supported by JSPS Research Fellowships for Young Scientists (DC1) (Nos. 25KJ2117) to R. N. Part of this study was supported by JST ACT-X (Nos. JPMJAX22AL) to T. Y. and CREST (Nos. JPMJCR21O1) to M. K. and Y. I.

References

- [1] B. Flebus, D. Grundler, B. Rana, Y. Otani, I. Barsukov, A. Barman, G. Gubbiotti, P. Landeros, J. Akerman, U. Ebels, P. Pirro, V. E. Demidov, K. Schultheiss, G. Csaba, Q. Wang, F. Ciubotaru, D. E. Nikonov, P. Che, R. Hertel, T. Ono, D. Afanasiev, J. Mentink, T. Rasing, B. Hillebrands, S. V. Kusminskiy, W. Zhang, C. R. Du, A. Finco, T. van der Sar, Y. K. Luo, Y. Shiota, J. Sklenar, T. Yu, and J. Rao, “The 2024 magnonics roadmap,” *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter*, vol. 36, p. 363501, Sept. 2024.
- [2] A. V. Chumak, P. Kabos, M. Wu, C. Abert, C. Adelman, A. O. Adeyeye, J. Akerman, F. G. Aliev, A. Anane, A. Awad, C. H. Back, A. Barman, G. E. W. Bauer, M. Becherer, E. N. Beginin, V. A. S. V. Bittencourt, Y. M. Blanter, P. Bortolotti, I. Boventer, D. A. Bozhko, S. A. Bunyaev, J. J. Carmiggelt, R. R. Cheenikundil, F. Ciubotaru, S. Cotofana, G. Csaba, O. V. Dobrovolskiy, C. Dubs, M. Elyasi, K. G. Fripp, H. Fulara, I. A. Golovchanskiy, C. Gonzalez-Ballester, P. Graczyk, D. Grundler, P. Gruszecki, G. Gubbiotti, K. Guslienko, A. Haldar, S. Hamdioui, R. Hertel, B. Hillebrands, T. Hioki, A. Houshang, C.-M. Hu, H. Huebl, M. Huth, E. Iacocca, M. B. Jungfleisch, G. N. Kakazei, A. Khitun, R. Khymyn, T. Kikkawa, M. Klau, O. Klein, J. W. Klos, S. Knauer, S. Koraltan, M. Kostylev, M. Krawczyk, I. N. Krivorotov, V. V. Kruglyak, D. Lachance-Quirion, S. Ladak, R. Lebrun, Y. Li, M. Lindner, R. Macedo, S. Mayr, G. A. Melkov, S. Mieszczak, Y. Nakamura, H. T. Nembach, A. A. Nikitin, S. A. Nikitov, V. Novosad, J. A. Otalora, Y. Otani, A. Papp, B. Pigeau, P. Pirro, W. Porod, F. Porrati, H. Qin, B. Rana,

- T. Reimann, F. Riente, O. Romero-Isart, A. Ross, A. V. Sadovnikov, A. R. Safin, E. Saitoh, G. Schmidt, H. Schultheiss, K. Schultheiss, A. A. Serga, S. Sharma, J. M. Shaw, D. Suess, O. Surzhenko, K. Szulc, T. Taniguchi, M. Urbanek, K. Usami, A. B. Ustinov, T. van der Sar, S. van Dijken, V. I. Vasyuchka, R. Verba, S. V. Kusminskiy, Q. Wang, M. Weides, M. Weiler, S. Wintz, S. P. Wolski, and X. Zhang, “Advances in magnetics roadmap on spin-wave computing,” *IEEE Trans. Magn.*, vol. 58, pp. 1–72, June 2022.
- [3] A. Khitun, M. Bao, and K. L. Wang, “Magnonic logic circuits,” *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, vol. 43, p. 264005, July 2010.
- [4] N. Kanazawa, T. Goto, K. Sekiguchi, A. B. Granovsky, C. A. Ross, H. Takagi, Y. Nakamura, and M. Inoue, “Demonstration of a robust magnonic spin wave interferometer,” *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 6, p. 30268, July 2016.
- [5] Y. Fan, M. J. Gross, T. Fakhrul, J. Finley, J. T. Hou, S. Ngo, L. Liu, and C. A. Ross, “Coherent magnon-induced domain-wall motion in a magnetic insulator channel,” *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, vol. 18, pp. 1000–1004, Sept. 2023.
- [6] Á. Papp, W. Porod, and G. Csaba, “Nanoscale neural network using non-linear spin-wave interference,” *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 12, p. 6422, Nov. 2021.
- [7] S. Nagase, S. Nezu, and K. Sekiguchi, “Spin-wave reservoir chips with short-term memory for high-speed estimation of external magnetic fields,” *Phys. Rev. Appl.*, vol. 22, p. 024072, Aug. 2024.
- [8] W. Namiki, D. Nishioka, T. Tsuchiya, and K. Terabe, “Fast physical reservoir computing, achieved with nonlinear interfered spin waves,” *Neuromorph. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 4, p. 024015, June 2024.
- [9] J. C. Gartside, K. D. Stenning, A. Vanstone, H. H. Holder, D. M. Arroo, T. Dion, F. Caravelli, H. Kurebayashi, and W. R. Branford, “Reconfigurable training and reservoir computing in an artificial spin-vortex ice via spin-wave fingerprinting,” *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, vol. 17, pp. 460–469, May 2022.
- [10] L. KÄúrber, C. Heins, T. Hula, J.-V. Kim, S. Thlang, H. Schultheiss, J. Fassbender, and K. Schultheiss, “Pattern recognition in reciprocal space with a magnon-scattering reservoir,” *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 14, p. 3954, July 2023.
- [11] A. V. Chumak, P. Pirro, A. A. Serga, M. P. Kostylev, R. L. Stamps, H. Schultheiss, K. Vogt, S. J. Hermsdoerfer, B. Laegel, P. A. Beck, and B. Hillebrands, “Spin-wave propagation in a microstructured magnonic crystal,” *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 95, p. 262508, Dec. 2009.

- [12] K. Mori, T. Koguchi, T. Watanabe, Y. Yoshihara, H. Miyashita, D. Grundler, M. Inoue, K. Ishiyama, and T. Goto, “Orientation-dependent two-dimensional magnonic crystal modes in an ultralow-damping ferrimagnetic waveguide containing repositioned hexagonal lattices of cu disks,” *Phys. Rev. Appl.*, vol. 21, p. 014061, Jan. 2024.
- [13] M. Krawczyk and H. Puzskarski, “Plane-wave theory of three-dimensional magnonic crystals,” *Phys. Rev. B*, vol. 77, p. 054437, Feb. 2008.
- [14] A. Rashedi, M. Ebrahimi, Y. Huang, M. J. Rudd, J. P. Davis, and V. A. S. V. Bittencourt, “Photonic crystal cavities based on suspended yttrium iron garnet nanobeams,” *Phys. Rev. Appl.*, vol. 24, p. 054017, Nov. 2025.
- [15] L. Liao, J. Liu, J. Puebla, Q. Shao, and Y. Otani, “Hybrid magnon-phonon crystals,” *npj Spintronics*, vol. 2, pp. 1–6, Sept. 2024.
- [16] D. Prajapati and C. Banerjee, “Selective spin-wave nonreciprocity in an engineered chiral magnonic crystal without dzyaloshinskii-moriya interaction,” *Phys. Rev. B.*, vol. 110, p. 224410, Dec. 2024.
- [17] G. Park, J. Yang, and S.-K. Kim, “Recursive evolution of spin-wave multiplets in magnonic crystals of antidot-lattice fractals,” *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 11, p. 22604, Nov. 2021.
- [18] A. De, K. Dutta, S. Mondal, S. Barman, Y. Otani, and A. Barman, “Magnonic crystals with complex geometry,” *Phys. Rev. B.*, vol. 103, Feb. 2021.
- [19] H. Yang, G. Yun, and Y. Cao, “Flatbands of spin waves in two-dimensional magnonic crystals with kagome lattices,” *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 137, p. 113904, Mar. 2025.
- [20] J. W. KÁĆos, M. L. Sokolovskyy, S. Mamica, and M. Krawczyk, “The impact of the lattice symmetry and the inclusion shape on the spectrum of 2D magnonic crystals,” *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 111, p. 123910, June 2012.
- [21] H. Yang, G. Yun, and Y. Cao, “Spin-wave band gaps created by rotating square rods in two-dimensional magnonic crystals,” *J. Phys. D Appl. Phys.*, vol. 44, p. 455001, Nov. 2011.
- [22] Z. K. Wang, V. L. Zhang, H. S. Lim, S. C. Ng, M. H. Kuok, S. Jain, and A. O. Adeyeye, “Nanostructured magnonic crystals with size-tunable bandgaps,” *ACS Nano*, vol. 4, pp. 643–648, Feb. 2010.
- [23] Q. Wang, Z. Zhong, L. Jin, X. Tang, F. Bai, and H. Zhang, “Large magnon band gaps created by introducing additional lattice scatterers,” *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 113, p. 153905, Apr. 2013.
- [24] M. Kiechle, L. Maucha, V. Ahrens, C. Dubs, W. Porod, G. Csaba, M. Becherer, and A. Papp, “Experimental demonstration of a spin-wave lens designed with machine learning,” *IEEE Magn. Lett.*, vol. 13, pp. 1–5, 2022.

- [25] Q. Wang, A. V. Chumak, and P. Pirro, “Inverse-design magnonic devices,” *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 12, p. 2636, May 2021.
- [26] N. Zenbaa, F. Majcen, C. Abert, F. Bruckner, N. J. Mauser, T. Schrefl, Q. Wang, D. Suess, and A. V. Chumak, “Realization of inverse-design magnonic logic gates,” *Sci. Adv.*, vol. 11, p. eadu9032, May 2025.
- [27] N. Zenbaa, C. Abert, F. Majcen, M. Kerber, R. O. Serha, S. Knauer, Q. Wang, T. Schrefl, D. Suess, and A. V. Chumak, “A universal inverse-design magnonic device,” *Nat. Electron.*, Jan. 2025.
- [28] A. A. Voronov, M. Cuervo Santos, F. Bruckner, D. Suess, A. V. Chumak, and C. Abert, “Inverse-design topology optimization of magnonic devices using level-set method,” *Npj Spintron.*, vol. 3, p. 19, May 2025.
- [29] F. Bruckner, S. Koraltan, C. Abert, and D. Suess, “magnum.np: a PyTorch based GPU enhanced finite difference micromagnetic simulation framework for high level development and inverse design,” *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 13, p. 12054, July 2023.
- [30] C. Abert, F. Bruckner, A. Voronov, M. Lang, S. A. Pathak, S. Holt, R. Kraft, R. Allayarov, P. Flauger, S. Koraltan, T. Schrefl, A. Chumak, H. Fangohr, and D. Suess, “NeuralMag: an open-source nodal finite-difference code for inverse micromagnetics,” *Npj Comput. Mater.*, vol. 11, p. 193, June 2025.
- [31] D. Kumar, J. W. KÁĆos, M. Krawczyk, and A. Barman, “Magnonic band structure, complete bandgap, and collective spin wave excitation in nanoscale two-dimensional magnonic crystals,” *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 115, p. 043917, Jan. 2014.
- [32] J. Romero Vivas, S. Mamica, M. Krawczyk, and V. V. Kruglyak, “Investigation of spin wave damping in three-dimensional magnonic crystals using the plane wave method,” *Phys. Rev. B Condens. Matter Mater. Phys.*, vol. 86, Oct. 2012.
- [33] J. Zhang, W. Yu, X. Chen, and J. Xiao, “A frequency-domain micromagnetic simulation module based on COMSOL multiphysics,” *AIP Adv.*, vol. 13, May 2023.
- [34] Y. Cao, G. Yun, X. Liang, and N. Bai, “Band structures of two-dimensional magnonic crystals with different shapes and arrangements of scatterers,” *J. Phys. D Appl. Phys.*, vol. 43, p. 305005, Aug. 2010.
- [35] D. D. Stancil and A. Prabhakar, *Spin waves*. New York, NY: Springer, 2009 ed., Apr. 2009.
- [36] S. Heiles and R. L. Johnston, “Global optimization of clusters using electronic structure methods,” *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, vol. 113, pp. 2091–2109, Sept. 2013.

- [37] O. Sigmund and K. Hougaard, “Geometric properties of optimal photonic crystals,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, vol. 100, p. 153904, Apr. 2008.
- [38] X. K. Han and Z. Zhang, “Topological optimization of phononic crystal thin plate by a genetic algorithm,” *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 9, p. 8331, June 2019.
- [39] “The MathWorks, inc. (2025). MATLAB version: 25.2.0 (R2025b).” <https://www.mathworks.com/>. Accessed: 2026-2-8.
- [40] Q. Wang, H. Zhang, X. Tang, H. Su, F. Bai, Y. Jing, and Z. Zhong, “Effects of symmetry reduction on magnon band gaps in two-dimensional magnonic crystals,” *J. Phys. D Appl. Phys.*, vol. 47, p. 065004, Feb. 2014.
- [41] A. Vansteenkiste, J. Leliaert, M. Dvornik, M. Helsen, F. Garcia-Sanchez, and B. Van Waeyenberge, “The design and verification of MuMax3,” *AIP Adv.*, vol. 4, p. 107133, Oct. 2014.
- [42] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and E. Duchesnay, “Scikit-learn: Machine learning in python,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 12, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.
- [43] T.-J. Cui, S. Liu, and L.-L. Li, “Information entropy of coding metasurface,” *Light Sci. Appl.*, vol. 5, p. e16172, Nov. 2016.